

MODELLING AND OPTIMIZATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN HEAT TREATMENT OF AISI 1045 USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT: This work is an experimental contribution followed by an optimization in order to examine heat treatment effect on hardness variances of AISI 1045 structural steel. Temperature (°C), holding time (min.) and cooling rate (slow, very fast) are the main input control parameters selected for the present investigation. A Taguchi L32 experimental plan is applied to determine the resulting influence in terms of Vickers hardness (HV), a principal mechanical property to assess heat treatment effectiveness. Percentage contribution for each control parameter is calculated using ANOVA with 95 % confidence interval. It is found that fast cooling is the most dominant factor on HV followed by temperature level. An optimization is presented based upon response surface methodology (RSM) and the desirability function (DF) approach in order to highlight the conditions which confer the best overall mechanical strength of such steel.

KEYWORDS: AISI structural steel; Heat treatments; Vickers Hardness; ANOVA; RSM; Optimization

1 INTRODUCTION

Among metallic materials, steels play a major part in determining modern engineering functions based on the various looked-for properties, the wide range of applications and the relative moderate production costs. AISI 1045 steel is an unalloyed medium carbon steel, which is also a general purpose carbon engineering steel. It is a medium strength steel showing an interesting good machinability and excellent tensile properties [1-5]. It is widely used in the automobile industry, in construction projects and in some other fields. In the initial state of carbon steel formation, the mixture of carbon and iron forms ferrite as the main component of the steel. The ferrite contained in such steels makes the metal more ductile, but its hardness usually remains at extremely minimal values.

It is accepted that heat treatment processes have made it possible to ameliorate the performance of steels owing to the increased demand from industries and also to the easiness for massive production. To use an alloy, it is necessary to make a balanced choice between the desired properties and those which are unwanted in order to concert certain concessions and obtain a compromise between

sought properties [6-7]. Therefore, heat treatment processes are of paramount importance in metallic product design stages.

Nowadays, heat treatments of steels have become an compulsory step when designing a given product [8]. They are generally composed of a heating phase, then a cooling down phase to room temperature. They make it possible to reveal and exploit certain properties of steel, such as hardness for example.

Techniques of experimental design are being used in different fields such as engineering [9-11], chemistry [12] and pharmaceutical and biomedical analyses [13]. such approach is a very popular methodology of planning and conducting experiments to search for a maximum efficiency using the smallest number of trials, and therefore ensuring the objective of the minimum cost. Statistical methods of experimental design aim at improving and optimizing the effectiveness and productivity of empirically conducted experiments. Computers and softwares participated to the rapid construction of experimental designs and provided the necessary calculations to make their interpretation very simple [14-16].

In the present investigation, we will determine the mathematical model of Vickers hardness HV. This

model makes it possible to highlight the relationship between the experimental elements of the heat treatment parameters, i.e., temperature, holding time and cooling and the Vickers hardness response. Then, the results are treated statistically in order to provide an optimal material rigidity. To achieve this objective, the response surface methodology (RSM) is adopted.

The paper is structured as follows: in section two, the experimental procedure is detailed. The statistical treatment of the data and the correlations between parameters obtained from the nonlinear regression are presented in section three. A graphical analysis of the observed values using Design-Expert is given in section four, and finally, optimization of responses is discussed in section five. The paper ends with concluding remarks and a conclusion.

2 MATERIAL, MEASUREMENT AND METHOD

2.1 Heat treatment of steel

Heat treatments can be performed for most materials within limited temperature ranges. These treatments are set to modify the crystalline structures of metals and their alloys and also particular materials such as plastics, glasses and ceramics. The

process offers great possibilities for certain technical industrial advantages as well as economic gains. At least, six strengthening heat treatment methods are available and they include (i) solid solution strengthening; (ii) strain hardening, (iii) grain size refinement; (iv) precipitation hardening; (v) dispersion hardening and (vi) phase transformations. All these methods are invoked to arrest the slip activity along slip planes to avoid plastic deformation and to obtain fine microstructures that make steels yet stronger.

2.2 Materials

Carbon steels belong to a category of steels with 0.12 to 2.0% carbon content. AISI 1045 steel, selected for this study, is a medium carbon steel designed for service in areas requiring greater strength and hardness. For the needs of heat treatments and hardness tests, cylindrical samples with an initial diameter of 22 mm and an initial height of 13 mm are prepared. The chemical composition of AISI 1045 is given in Table 1. It is general purpose steel grade and common applications include manufacturing of bolts, studs, gears, axles, shafts and other machine parts. Some mechanical properties of AISI 1045 are listed in Table 2.

Table 1. Chemical composition of AISI 1045 steel.

% C	% Si	%Mn	% P	% S	%Cr	%Ni	%Al
0.42-0.50	0.35	0.8	0.04	0.045	0.40	0.40	0.02

Table 2. Typical mechanical properties of AISI 1045 steel.

Tensile strength (MPa)	Yield strength (MPa)	Elasticity modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Shear modulus (GPa)	Elongation (%)
585	450	200	0.29	80	12

2.3 Mechanical polishing

After heat treatment process, polishing is performed in order to obtain a smooth and mirror-like surface. The samples are polished with paper of particle size varying from 180 to 1000 under lubrication until surface is bright and free of any stripes as required.

2.4 Hardness test

The Vickers hardness test is one of the oldest methods used to test the hardness of metals and alloys especially when heat treatment is associated. In this study, Vickers hardness is evaluated using a digital micro hardness tester HVS-1000Z. All tests

are carried out on previously polished samples under a consistent load of 20 kgf applied for approximately 10 seconds. All hardness tests were carried out on the external faces of the samples. A minimum of four readings are taken for each sample, and the average is derived. The hardness of the workpiece is HV142.

2.5 Organization of experiments

Most investigators design their experimental plans with the objective of reducing resources and time without compromising quality. The response surface methodology (RSM), a procedure aimed at determining a relationship between independent

input process parameters and output ones or process responses, is applied. It includes six essential steps which are given as follows: (i) define the independent input variables and the desired output responses; (ii) adopt an experimental design plan; (iii) perform regression analysis with the quadratic model of RSM; (iv) perform a statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the independent input variables in order to find parameters which affect the most significantly response; (v) determine the situation of the RSM model and decide whether this model needs screening variables or not; and finally, (vi) optimize and conduct confirmation experiment and verifying the predicted performance characteristics. The experiments' setups are shown in Figure 1. A Taguchi-based orthogonal array capable of simultaneously and individually evaluating two or more parameters affecting the variability of a given process characteristic using a minimal number of tests is adopted. Taking these control factors into account, an orthogonal L32 cluster is shown to be suitable.

Fig. 1. Experimental methodology.

Tests were performed according to four levels of temperature (800, 850, 870 and 900 °C), holding time (20, 40, 60 and 120 min) and two levels of cooling (slow, and fast cooling) as shown in Table 3. Water quenching was done to achieve a very fast cooling rate. Initial temperature of water was measured as 22°C. All the heated samples were dipped into water for 30 min. In this work an automatic micro-hardness meter with Vickers penetration is used as shown in Figure 1.

Table 3. Input parameters and their levels.

Levels	Temperature, T(°C)	Holding time, t(min)	Cooling process
1	800	20	Air
2	850	40	
3	870	60	water
4	900	120	

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4 presents the hardness measurements according to the Taguchi L₃₂ approach.

Table 4. Vickers hardness results.

Run Order	Temperature, T (°C)	Holding time, t (min)	Cooling process	Vickers hardness (HV)
1	800	20	Air	167.14
2	800	40	Air	173.84
3	800	60	Air	174.53
4	800	120	Air	176.2
5	850	20	Air	171.26
6	850	40	Air	173,36
7	850	60	Air	173.2
8	850	120	Air	181,67
9	870	20	Air	168.7
10	870	40	Air	169.8
11	870	60	Air	183.9
12	870	120	Air	222.57
13	900	20	Air	264.2
14	900	40	Air	277.5
15	900	60	Air	280.8
16	900	120	Air	282.3
17	800	20	Water	275.87
18	800	40	Water	290.6
19	800	60	Water	321.88
20	800	120	Water	332.3
21	850	20	Water	325.6
22	850	40	Water	364.3
23	850	60	Water	369.6
24	850	120	Water	388.2

25	870	20	Water	327.57
26	870	40	Water	339.77
27	870	60	Water	376.13
28	870	120	Water	384
29	900	20	Water	267.23
30	900	40	Water	280.57
31	900	60	Water	339.96
32	900	120	Water	410.56

3.1 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for Vickers hardness (HV)

Analysis of variance is a statistical approach used in many scientific fields to analyse group averages and interactions [17-21]. The analysis of variance for the Vickers hardness (HV) as well as the estimated regression coefficients are presented in the Table 5.

The mentioned values are the sum of squares (SS), degrees of freedom (DF), mean square (MS), F-value and probability (P-value) in addition to the percentage contribution (Contr.%) of each factor. The greater the percentage of contribution (PC %), the greater the factor that has an effect on the studied parameters. ANOVA results for HV as reported in Table 5, reveal that the main contribution is performed by the cooling (73.87%) followed by the temperature and the holding time with 7.81% and 4.93% respectively. They are followed by the temperature-holding time interaction with a contribution of 2.2% while the remaining parameters did not show any significant influence on the Vickers hardness (HV). Some researchers in the literature indicate that the heat treatment processes, and cooling rate have a great effect on the mechanical properties of AISI 1045 steel [22-23].

Table 5. Analysis of variance for HV.

Source	SS	MS	F Value	PC %	p-value	Remarks
Model	180300	30050.58	31.12		< 0.0001	significant
A-Temperature	15965.54	15965.54	16.54	7.81%	0.0004	significant
B-Holding time	10080.34	10080.34	10.44	4.93%	0.0034	significant
C-Cooling	151000	151000	156.35	73.87%	< 0.0001	significant
AB	1483.98	1483.98	1.54	1%	0.2266	Not significant
AC	4548.22	4548.22	4.71	2.2%	0.0397	significant
BC	3502.02	3502.02	3.63	1.71%	0.0684	Not significant
A2	187.68	187.68	0.18	0%	0.67	Not significant
B2	538.06	538.06	0.53	0%	0.4745	Not significant
Residual	24138.84	965.55				
Cor Total	204400					
Source	SS	MS	F Value	PC %	p-value	Remarks
Model	180300	30050.58	31.12		< 0.0001	significant

R²: 0,88 Adj R²:0,84

3.2 Regression equations

The nonlinear relationships between input and output variables are established using regression analysis. Soft computing based approach is used to optimize the better rigidity of AISI 1045 steel. The relationship between inputs, heat treatment parameters and the output Y is also analyzed. The

output Y characterizes the Vickers hardness; it is given by Eq. (1) :

$$Y = H(\text{temperature, holding time, cooling process}) + e_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where Y is the desired response and H is the response hardness. In this particular case, the approximation of Y is proposed by using the fitted second order polynomial regression model called the

quadratic model. The quadratic model of Y is given by Eq. (2):

$$Y = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=0}^k \alpha_i X_i + \sum_{i=0}^k \alpha_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i < j}^k \alpha_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (2)$$

where explicitly, Y: is the estimated response (hardness HV). α_0 , α_i , α_{ij} and α_{ii} are the adopted mathematical model coefficients. They are not identified and must be calculated from the experimental results. X_i are variables or factors that influence the response (Y), corresponding to the studied heat treatment parameters such as temperature T (°C), holding time t (min), cooling and their interactions.

Mathematical equations of the fitted models for the Vickers hardness (HV) models with fast and slow cooling are given below in Eq. (3) and Eq. (4) respectively.

$$Hv_{WC} = +326,33 - 0,04 \times T - 3,49 \times t + 0,00499 \times T \times t \quad (3)$$

$$Hv_{AC} = -334,74 + 0,612 \times T - 4,05 \times t + 0,00499 \times T \times t \quad (4)$$

R2 value of the model is 88 %, which shows that the model can explain 88 % of total variations in heat treatment.

Fig. 2. Measured vs. Predicted values of heat treatment a) Air-cooling b) Water-cooling.

Figure 2 (a) and (b) illustrate the differences between measured and predicted responses. It is concluded that the nonlinear models are capable for representing the system under the given experimental domain. The comparison results prove that predicted values of different heat treatment of steel are closer to those readings recorded experimentally.

3.3 Residual analysis

Figure 3 shows the normal probability of residuals. It reveals that all the residual points are falling in a straight line which means, the errors are normally distributed. This indicates that the developed regression model is acceptable under given experimental range.

Fig. 3. Normal Probability residuals for Hardness HV.

3.4 Surface plots

The version 10 of the Design-Expert Software is used to develop the experimental plan for response surface methodology. Figure 4 illustrates the estimated response surface plots for Vickers hardness (HV) versus the heat treatment parameters (namely holding time, temperature and water-cooling). It can be observed that the Vickers hardness rapidly increases with increasing temperature and holding time. It is found that the highest hardness value lays within the temperature interval [860 – 900 °C].

The appearance of martensitic structure, a supersaturated solution of carbon in alpha iron, causes a deformation of the crystal lattice by shearing of the austenite network. It follows the appearance of strong constraints which generate the increase in hardness. Similar explanations have been mentioned by [24-25] regarding the effect of the heat treatment parameter on the martensite phenomenon.

Fig. 4. Estimated response surface for Hardness versus holding time and temperature (water-cooling).

Fig. 5. Estimated response surface for Hardness versus holding time and temperature (air-cooling).

Figure 5 shows the estimated response surface plots for Vickers hardness HV versus the heat treatment parameters (namely holding time, temperature and air-cooling). It can be observed that the Vickers hardness rapidly increases with increasing temperature. Optimum heat treatment conditions that maximize Vickers hardness are found to be at T=900°C, t = 120 min and water-cooling. Moreover, the highest Vickers hardness (HV = 410.56) is achieved at the highest temperature and the longest holding time. These results are in perfect agreement with published literature work [26-27].

4 DESIRABILITY STUDY AND OPTIMIZATION

G. Derringer and R. Suich proposed desirability function method in 1980 and it gained a large acceptance for response prediction assessments. The desirability function method is nowadays used in several applications such as engineering [28], operational research [29], economics and management [30] and even in biochemistry [31]. A dimensionless desirability value (D) for each response variable $f(y)$, where y is the input variables, is measured by transforming the predicted response. This approach allows the combination of multiple

responses into a single function (the Desirability Function or DF) through the choice of a value comprised between 0 and 1 (least to most desirable respectively). Optimization methods need to be used to obtain the optimum heat treatment conditions on mechanical properties using Vickers hardness as responses.

Here, the goal is to maximize Vickers hardness (HV). To resolve this type of parameter design problem, an objective function, $F(x)$, is defined as follows [32]:

$$DF = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n d_i^{w_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^n w_j}} \quad (5)$$

$$F(x) = -DF$$

where d_i is the desirability defined for the i^{th} targeted output and w_i is the weighting of d_i . For various goals of each targeted output, the desirability, d_i , is defined in different forms. If a goal is to reach a specific value of T_i , the desirability d_i is:

$$d_i = 0 \text{ if } Y_i \leq Low_i$$

$$d_i = \left[\frac{Y_i - Low_i}{T_i - Low_i} \right] \text{ if } Low_i \leq Y_i \leq T_i \quad (6)$$

$$d_i = \left[\frac{Y_i - High_i}{T_i - High_i} \right] \text{ if } T_i \leq Y_i \leq High_i$$

$$d_i = 0 \text{ if } Y_i \geq High_i$$

For a goal to find a maximum, the desirability is shown as follows:

$$d_i = 0 \text{ if } Y_i \leq Low_i$$

$$d_i = \left[\frac{Y_i - Low_i}{High_i - Low_i} \right] \text{ if } Low_i \leq Y_i \leq High_i \quad (7)$$

$$d_i = 1 \text{ if } Y_i \geq High_i$$

where the Y_i is the found value of the i^{th} output during optimization processes; the Low_i and the $High_i$ are, respectively, the minimum and the maximum values of the experimental data for the i^{th} output. In Eq. (5), w_i is set to one since the d_i is equally important in this study. The DF is a combined desirability function [31], and the objective is to choose an optimal setting that maximizes a combined desirability function DF , i.e., minimizes $F(x)$.

Fig. 6. Ramp of desirability function for Vickers hardness.

Figure 6 shows the ramp diagram with the exact optimal values of the input parameters (temperature, holding time and cooling) and the output technology parameter (Vickers hardness) along with the desirability for the case studied. In fact, the optimal heat treatment parameters are achieved with maximum value of (HV=409.23) when equal weights are set as a desired condition. Moreover, the point displaying the highest desirability is shown in Figure 7, and is represented by T=900°C, t=120 min, and cooling water. The optimal regions taking the overall desirability value of 0.995 indicate closeness to the target response.

Fig. 7. Results of the desirability function.

5 CONCLUSION

When exploiting efficiently designed experiments, the conditions that give the best possible precision with the smallest number of runs are usually guaranteed. This optimization of the heat treatment process of AISI 1045 steel in terms of hardness allows to formulate the following conclusions:

1. The analysis of the heat treatment parameters through the application of the Response Surface Methodology approach allowed the exploration of the influence of each factor on the response outputs represented in the present case by Vickers hardness (HV).
2. Only a small number of experiments are required to generate helpful information exploited for predicting Vickers hardness equations.
3. The high R^2 value of the model shows that it can explain 88 % of total variations in heat treatment. Consequently, a good agreement is found between the proposed theoretical models and the obtained experimental data.
4. The Statistical analysis (ANOVA) led to conclude that the most influential factors on the evolution of the Vickers hardness are represented by the cooling and the temperature with contributions reaching 57% and 7.81% on (HV) respectively.
5. Response optimization shows that the optimal heat treatment parameters are represented by a temperature of 900°C, a holding time of 120 min and a cooling process based on water. The optimized parameter Vickers hardness is HV = 409.23.
6. Results showed that as the cooling rate of the steel increase, the hardness of the steel is also increased.
7. The developed mathematical model can fully assist in predicting steel rigidity variations as a function of the level changes of different input parameters. Also, it is useful for setting the optimum value of the parameters to achieve the targeted rigidity.

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